

MEASURING THE INSULATING RESISTANCE IN NETWORKS WITH ISOLATED STAR CENTRE CONTROLLED BY AN AZUR DEVICE

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ABSTRACT. The AZUR apparatus is intended to control the insulating resistance in mine networks with an isolated star centre. The indication of the measured insulating resistance is realised by a pointer meter with a reversed nonlinear scale, which makes it difficult to read. The methodology for the development of an analogue converter is considered here, which linearises the non-linear characteristic current-resistance and, together with a light indicator, the device allows for more accurate and easy reading. An analysis of the error and the measurement range is made.

Keywords: insulating resistance control, mine power networks, measuring analogue converter.

Introduction

The insulating resistance control apparatus in networks with an isolated star centre is designed to create a stable constant operational voltage U_{ref} on the general insulating resistance between the phases and ground. The diagram and the coupling of the apparatus are not subject of this paper.

The simplest AZUR equivalent circuit, on the basis of which the characteristic has been analysed, is given in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit for measuring the insulating resistance in AZUR

The milliamp meter measures the current I , which depends on, R_{ins} while its scale, highly non-linear and reverse, is divided into segments in $k\Omega$. The AZUR apparatus is often mounted in an explosion protected casing and the slightly illuminated appliance is observed through a thick glass, which makes it difficult to read the insulating resistance. In addition, the accuracy is unsatisfactory – there is about 10% relative error.

The present paper aims to describe a non-linear analogue converter, which allows the insulating resistance R_{ins} to be transformed into voltage E , which is strictly proportional to it, measured by a digital voltmeter with a LED display. The number of the display is equal to the value of R_{ins} , in $k\Omega$.

First stage - Block I

The first stage of the converter is the AZUR device itself, in which the milliamp meter is replaced by one resistance with an accuracy of 1%, $R_m = 100 \Omega$.

Figure 2 presents Block I, in which the input value is the insulating resistance R_{ins} , and the output value is the drop of voltage over $R_m \rightarrow U_R = 100 \cdot I$. The resistance R_m is selected with a small value compared to the other resistances in the circuit, so that it does not significantly affect the measured current.

Fig. 2. Block I, input value R_{ins} - insulating resistance, output value U_R - voltage over R_m

The current I is determined by the circuit in Figure 1 and given as::

$$I = \frac{160}{20 \cdot 10^3 + 200 \cdot 10^3 // R_{ins}} \quad (1)$$

The contour resistance is made up of a R_{ins} connected in parallel to $200 k\Omega$ plus $20 k\Omega$. The operative voltage $U_{OP} = 160 V$ is stabilised. The U_R voltage is a non -linear decreasing R_{ins} function that is close in shape to a hyperbola. When the input value, the argument of the R_{ins} function grows, the U_R (R_{ins}) function decreases according to the nonlinear dependence (1).

Let's now set the boundaries of change of R_{ins} and U_R .

The scope of R_{ins} is set from $20 k\Omega$ to $200 k\Omega$. Resistance below $20 k\Omega$ cannot be measured as AZUR switches off the power supply upon deterioration of the insulating resistance up to $20 k\Omega$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At } R_{ins} &= 20 k\Omega \\ U_R &= U_R^{20} = \\ &= 100 \frac{160}{20 \cdot 10^3 + 200 \cdot 10^3 // 20 \cdot 10^3} = 0.419 V \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At } R_{ins} &= 200 k\Omega \\ U_R &= U_R^{200} = \\ &= 100 \frac{160}{20 \cdot 10^3 + 200 \cdot 10^3 // 200 \cdot 10^3} = 0.133 V \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The change of U_R is equal to

$$\Delta U_R = U_R^{20} - U_R^{200} = 0.419 - 0.133 = 0.286 V \quad (4)$$

The transfer function of Block I

$$U_R = 100 \cdot I(R_{ins})$$

is graphically presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Transmitting function of Block I

U_R is a decreasing, non-linear function of the measured magnitude of the insulating resistance R_{ins} . As shown in (4) it changes in the interval $\Delta U_R = 0.286 \text{ V}$.

Second stage - Block II

The purpose of Block II is to convert the decreasing $U_R(R_{ins})$ function into an increasing one $U(R_{ins})$ by amplification, inverting and summing up. It consists of an amplifier with a gain k , source of constant voltage U_0 and an adder. The functional diagram of Block II is shown in Figure 4.

The output voltage U should be normalised. As R_{ins} increases ten times from an initial value (20k) to a final one (200k), hence U should increase 10 times accordingly. The change interval of U is determined to be from 1 V to 10 V, i.e. $\Delta U = 9 \text{ V}$

Next, the gain k and the U_0 value are determined. Since U_R is an input voltage and U is an output voltage for Block II

$$k = \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta U_R} = \frac{9}{0.286} = 31.5 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 4. Functional diagram of Block II

$$U = U_0 - kU_R \quad (5')$$

The initial value of U is 1 V.

$$1 = U_0 - kU_R^{20} = U_0 - 31.5 \cdot 0.419 = U_0 - 13.2 \quad (6)$$

The final value of U is 10 V.

$$10 = U_0 - kU_R^{200} = U_0 - 31.5 \cdot 0.133 = U_0 - 4.2 \quad (7)$$

From (6) and (7) the following value is obtained for U_0

$$U_0 = 14.2 \text{ V} \quad (8)$$

The graphs for the functions kU_R and U are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Graphs for the functions kU_R and U - Block II

The diagram of Block II is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Diagram of Block II

The circuit is an inverted amplifier-adder implemented with an operating amplifier (Rutkowski, 1975.)

LM385 is a source of reference voltage 2.5 V.

The three resistances R_0 , R_1 , R_2 are defined in the following way:

$$I_1 = \frac{U_R}{R_1} \quad (9)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{2.5}{R_2} \quad (10)$$

$$I_0 = I_1 - I_2 \quad (11)$$

$$U = -R_0 I_0 = -R_0 (I_1 - I_2) = R_0 I_2 - R_0 I_1 \quad (12)$$

From (5') $U = U_0 - kU_R$

When (12) and (5') are compared, the following expression is obtained:

$$U_0 = R_0 I_2 = R_0 \frac{2.5}{R_2} \quad (13)$$

The value of U_0 is 14.2 V.

The value 20 k Ω is chosen for R_0 .

From (13) the value of R_2 is defined:

$$14.2 = 20 \cdot 10^3 \cdot \frac{2.5}{R_2} \rightarrow R_2 = 3521 \Omega$$

$$kU_R = R_0 I_1 \quad (14)$$

[follows from (12) and (5')]

$$kU_R = R_0 \frac{U_R}{R_1},$$

U_R is cancelled

$$31.5 = 20 \cdot 10^3 \frac{1}{R_1} \rightarrow R_1 = \frac{20 \cdot 10^3}{31.5} = 635 \Omega$$

Third Stage - Block III

Block III should implement the reverse function between the input value U and the output value E . Thus, the straight function is $R_{ins} \rightarrow U$ and the reverse one is $U \rightarrow E$, where there should be linear dependence between R_{ins} and E .

The voltage U (R_{ins}) enters at the input of Block III. The graph of this dependency is shown in Figure 5, the values of the argument (independent magnitude) R_{ins} are plotted to the x-axis and the values of the function U are plotted to the y-axis.

We now take this characteristic experimentally by exchanging the places of the coordinate axes. The values of the argument R_{ins} are plotted to the y-axis and the corresponding values of U are plotted to the x-axis. In this operation, we get the reverse function of the $U(R_{ins})$ function. The R_{ins} values are set using decade resistance box, and the respective values of U are measured with an exact voltmeter at the outlet of Block II (Figure 6).

The graph is drawn on millimetre paper using 20 points and we try to approximate it with line segments. When the number of line segments is greater, the approximation is more accurate, but the circuit of Block III becomes too complicated.

Four line segments have been selected which are connected in three refraction points. This is done visually on the graph, trying to bring the line segment and the corresponding curve as close as possible.

Figure 7 shows the graph of the reverse function and its approximation through four line segments. The voltage U is in the range of 1 V to 10 V and the refraction points are 6 V, 8 V and 9 V.

The angle factors in the equations of the straight lines are K_0 , K_1 , K_2 and K_3 . These factors are defined by the graph and are respectively:

$$K_0 = \operatorname{tg} \alpha_0 = \frac{1}{3}; \quad \alpha_0 = 18.4^\circ$$

$$K_1 = \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 = \frac{3}{4}; \quad \alpha_1 = 36.9^\circ$$

$$K_2 = \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2 = 2; \quad \alpha_2 = 63.4^\circ$$

$$K_3 = \operatorname{tg} \alpha_3 = 5; \quad \alpha_3 = 78.7^\circ$$

The angles of the slope α_0 , α_1 , α_2 and α_3 are between the respective line segments and the x-axis (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Graph of the approximated function $U(R_{ins})$.

In fact, Block III implements the reverse function approximated through four line segments. It represents a linear amplifier with a changing gain. (Sheingolf, 1974) The line diagram is shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Line diagram of Block III

When changing U from 1V to 6V, the gain is K_0 and the three diodes are turned off.

$$K_0 = \frac{R_f}{R_0} \quad (15)$$

In the interval from 6 V to 8 V, diode D_1 is switched on and connects the resistance R_1 parallel to R_0 . The gain increases $K_1 > K_0$.

To define the values of the resistances R_0 , R_1 , R_2 and R_3 it is easier to work with the respective conductivities g_0 , g_1 , g_2 and g_3 .

$$K_0 = \frac{1}{3}, \quad K_0 = g_0 R_f \quad (15')$$

The value 10 kΩ is accepted for R_f .

$$R_f = 10000 \Omega$$

$$\frac{1}{3} = g_0 \cdot 10000 \quad g_0 = \frac{1}{30000} \text{ S}$$

$$R_0 = 30 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$K_1 = \frac{3}{4}, \quad K_1 = (g_0 + g_1)R_f = K_0 + g_1R_f \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{3}{4} = \frac{1}{3} + g_1 \cdot 10000$$

$$g_1 = \frac{3/4 - 1/3}{10000} = \frac{5}{120000} \text{ S}$$

$$R_1 = \frac{120000}{5} = 24000 \Omega$$

$$R_1 = 24 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$K_2 = 2; \quad K_2 = (g_0 + g_1 + g_2)R_f = K_1 + g_2R_f \quad (17)$$

$$2 = \frac{3}{4} + g_2 \cdot 10000$$

$$g_2 = \frac{2 - 3/4}{10000} = \frac{5}{40000} \text{ S}$$

$$R_2 = \frac{40000}{5} = 8000 \Omega$$

$$R_2 = 8 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$K_3 = 5; \quad K_3 = (g_0 + g_1 + g_2 + g_3)R_f = K_2 + g_3R_f \quad (18)$$

$$5 = 2 + g_3 \cdot 10000$$

$$g_3 = \frac{3}{10000} \text{ S}$$

$$R_3 = \frac{10000}{3} = 3333 \Omega$$

$$R_3 = 3.33 \text{ k}\Omega$$

Thus, the resistances which define the gain are:

$$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega;$$

$$R_0 = 30 \text{ k}\Omega; \quad R_1 = 24 \text{ k}\Omega;$$

$$R_2 = 8 \text{ k}\Omega; \quad R_3 = 3.33 \text{ k}\Omega$$

The resistances which define the thresholds of switching on of the respective diodes are R_A , R_B and R_C .

The diode D_1 is switched on when the potential of its anode is equal to zero as is the potential of the cathode. Shortly before D_1 is switched on, the current through R_1 and R_A is equal to:

$$I_A = \frac{6}{R_1} = \frac{2.5}{R_A}, \quad R_A = \frac{2.5}{6} \cdot 24000 \quad (19)$$

$$R_A = 10000 \Omega$$

It is assumed that the three diodes are ideal. R_B and R_C are defined in the same way.

$$I_B = \frac{8}{R_2} = \frac{2.5}{R_B}, \quad R_B = \frac{2.5}{8} \cdot 8000 \quad (20)$$

$$R_B = 2500 \Omega$$

$$I_C = \frac{9}{R_3} = \frac{2.5}{R_C}, \quad R_C = \frac{2.5}{9} \cdot 3333 \quad (21)$$

$$R_C = 926 \Omega$$

Thus, the resistances which define the refraction thresholds are:

$$R_A = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$R_B = 2.5 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$R_C = 926 \Omega$$

What needs to be explained now is why it is necessary to have one more reference source 2.5 V for the resistance R .

Since the graph on Figure 7 does not start from zero, it is necessary to change the coordinate system which is shown on Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Transformation of the coordinate system.

In the coordinate system $x-y$ the function is:

$$y = K_0 \cdot x \quad (22)$$

In the new coordinate system $X-Y$

$$Y = K_0 \cdot (X - 1) + 1, \quad (23)$$

where

$$K_0 = \frac{1}{3}, \quad x = X - 1,$$

then

$$Y = \frac{1}{3}X + \frac{2}{3} \quad (24)$$

From the expression (24) it can be seen that it is necessary to lift the whole graph up along the y -axis with $2/3$ V. This is done with a reference source 2.5 V and resistance R . The R value is defined in the following way:

$$2,5 \left(\frac{R_f}{R} \right) = \frac{2}{3} \quad \frac{2,5 \cdot 10000}{R} = \frac{2}{3} \quad (25)$$

$$R = 37500 \Omega$$

Thus, all resistances from the Block III circuit are defined (Figure 8).

At the output of Block III a voltage divider is connected and a digital voltmeter realised with HC ICL7107 and a display of LED $3 \frac{1}{2}$ digits (Faulkenberry, 1982.)

When the resistance is equal to 20 kΩ, the display shows 19.9 kΩ, at 200 kΩ - 199.9 kΩ. The decimal point does not move.

Defining the relative error

To define the biggest relative error in a given interval, the function $U_R(R_{ins})$ is presented in the following way:

$$U = 14,2 - 31,5 \frac{1,6 \cdot R_{ins} + 320}{22 \cdot R_{ins} + 400} \quad (26)$$

And respectively:

$$R_{ins} = \frac{400U + 4400}{262 - 22U}, \quad (27)$$

where R_{ins} is in kΩ.

An interval U (6 ÷ 8) V, whose average is 7 V (Figure 10), is selected as an example.

Fig. 10. A graph for defining the relative error.

We define the R_{ins} values in three points – 6, 7 and 8 V.

$$R_6 = \frac{400 \cdot 6 + 4400}{262 - 22 \cdot 6} = 52,3 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (28)$$

$$R_7 = \frac{400 \cdot 7 + 4400}{262 - 22 \cdot 7} = 66,6 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (29)$$

$$R_8 = \frac{400 \cdot 8 + 4400}{262 - 22 \cdot 8} = 88,4 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (30)$$

The exact value of R_{ins} is designated with R_T on Figure 10 and with R_a – the measured value on the line segment for approximation.

In the case:

$$R_T = R_7 = 66,6 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (31)$$

R_a is equal to the mean value from R_6 and R_8

$$R_a = \frac{52,3 + 88,4}{2} = 70,3 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (32)$$

The biggest relative error in the interval used as an example is:

$$\delta\% = \frac{R_a - R_T}{R_T} 100 = \frac{70,3 - 66,6}{66,6} 100 = 5,5\% \quad (33).$$

To conclude, it should be noted that if we want to achieve the smallest error due to the approximation, we should not use four line segments but five, or more precisely six.

All calculated resistances can be regulated. The setting procedure is not described as it is too long and is related to the practical implementation of the converter.

Conclusions

The developed device for measuring the insulation resistance is fully compatible with the AZUR device. It is realised by means of an analogue converter, which linearises the non-linear characteristics current-resistance. The applied light indicator allows for more accurate and easier reading of the insulation resistance in the grid. The measuring range and the relative error meet the requirements for control of the insulation resistance in mine electrical grid with isolated star centre.

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